

PECULIARITIES OF DETECTIVE GENRE

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Abstract: In this thesis the peculiarities of world detective fiction were explained and analyzed with examples.

Key words: requirements, detective genre, crime, criminal, conflicts, collisions, composition, poetics.

Introduction: Detective fiction is a genre of writing where a detective works to solve a crime. The audience is challenged to solve the crime by the clues provided before the detective reveals the answer at the end of the novel. This genre has its own place in world literature. Works in this genre should be write on the basis of special rules that are invariable.

Main part: Works in the detective genre demand the writer to fulfill a number of important requirements. After all, every work of art is considered a work worth reading by the reader only when it reflects its unique artistic features. From this point of view, the detective genre is considered a literary genre with its undeniable artistic features.

There have been many debates and discussions about the study and analysis of the specific features, forms, and traditions of detective literature. In the second half of the 19th century, the French sociologists Robert Escarpit and Regis Messac predicted that this genre would have a great position in the literature of the 20th century as a result of their research.

When we think of a detective story, the first thing that comes to mind is the "triple formula". To be more precise, the presence of "detective", "crime" and "criminal" in the work. In addition, in this type of works, the reference of facts to a

reader is also an important aspect. When the investigative process reaches its climax, the reader must have enough information to make his own decision. After the tests are over, you need to answer all the questions and solve the puzzle. Therefore, N. N. Volskiy described that "the detective world is more orderly than the life around us".

Skvovreskiy said: "Compared to other types of novels, detective stories do not usually end with a climax. Many explanations are offered for the crime to find its just and logical solution. The following conclusion can be drawn from these points: The detective is not only a dramatic story. Maybe it consists of problems waiting for their logical solution together with that story. Detective stories often end with a guilty plea. Some of the works also describe the punishment of the criminal and the court proceedings.

According to Hart, "The main structural feature of the detective genre is the disaster, and the murder is usually shown first. Then a number of clues are given for the suspected criminals to find the punishment for the crime. Allusions should be such that the reader will not have clear information until the criminal confesses or reveals exactly how the crime was committed. The story will be surrounded by mysterious events that will be revealed by the detective.

In detective works, the crime is mainly described in chronological order. However, the content of the story, criminal investigations and comments are not given in chronological order in order to attract the attention of the reader. Marcus explains it as follows: "A detective work is a set of signs and symbols that hide some secrets and wait for the detective to uncover them". This idea is reflected in the work of Raymond Chandler, who perfectly described the city of his time, full of secrets and hidden symbols, and the detective who fights against evil and chaos.

In general, all these are considered to be specific aspects of the composition of the detective genre. The creation of a composition is the primary factor for the success of any genre. As M. Koshjanov described, "Composition is the clarity of the focus of attention of the creators in the work, the clarity of the artistic idea, the

placement of large and small parts and images in the work, and their appropriateness and appropriateness of the image”.

According to Turob Toychievich Irisbojev, “detective literature requires a density of composition”. That is, as long as the episodes and events are not accelerated and condensed, the composition of the created work seems to contradict both detective-adventure literature and real life. If we look at the second book of Tahir Malik’s “Shaytanat”, it is not difficult to understand how the development of the plot takes a violent tone. The writer called “The last chapter of the third book” under the title “Asadbek, Elchin, Hosilboyvachcha. November 29, 1989”. From this comment, we can understand that these three named characters will participate in this chapter. In addition, the introduction of a specific time and date increases speed and precision, and warns the reader that events will take a violent tone.

The violent nature of the development of events depends on how skillfully the conflict and collisions are depicted in the work. These two concepts are factors that show the uniqueness of the detective work’s poetics. In detective works, conflict and collisions occur at the heart of sharp and dynamic, sequential and interconnected events. As the works written in this genre are based on very intense events, we witness more conflicts and collisions than in other genres. The work ‘Shaytanat’, which is considered a masterpiece of Uzbek prose, is extremely rich in conflicts and collisions.

Establishing a coherent system of events in fiction and describing the space, time and human situations in the plot, the development of events, problem, culmination and solution are also the characteristics of the work written in the detective genre. By observing the composition of the plot of a detective work, we can learn the artistic features of this genre.

Another important feature of the detective is that the true circumstances of the incident are not fully communicated to the reader until the end of the investigation. Instead, the reader is guided by the author through a research process where at each

stage they have the opportunity to create their own versions and evaluate certain facts. If the work initially describes all the details of the incident or there is nothing unusual or mysterious. It is considered to be a pure detective story.

Conclusion: Detective genre obeys the completeness of facts. Solving the mystery cannot be based on information not provided to the reader in the description of the investigation. After the investigation is complete, the reader should have enough information to base his decision on. Only a few small details that do not affect the possibility of revealing the secret can be hidden. After the investigation, all puzzles must be solved, all questions must be answered as well. In detective works, the way of setting the problem and the investigating process are noteworthy aspects.

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